

Development of a fully human assay combining NGN2-inducible neurons co-cultured with iPSC-derived astrocytes amenable for electrophysiological studies

Pei-Yu Shih^a, Mohamed Kreir^a, Devesh Kumar^a, Frederik Seibt^a, Francisco Pestana^a, Benjamin Schmid^b, Bjørn Holst^b, Christian Clausen^b, Rachel Steeg^c, Benjamin Fischer^d, Juan Pita-Almenar^a, Andreas Ebneith^a, Alfredo Cabrera-Socorro^{a,*}

^a Janssen Pharmaceutica NV, Turnhoutseweg 30, 2340 Beerse, Belgium

^b Bioneer S/A, Kogle Allé 2, 2970 Hørsholm, Denmark

^c Fraunhofer UK Research Ltd, Glasgow, UK

^d Project Centre for Stem Cell Process Engineering, Fraunhofer Institute for Biomedical Engineering IBMT, Würzburg, Germany

A B S T R A C T

Neurogenin 2 encodes a neural-specific transcription factor (NGN2) able to drive neuronal fate on somatic and stem cells. NGN2 is expressed in neural progenitors within the developing central and peripheral nervous systems. Overexpression of NGN2 in human induced pluripotent stem cells (hiPSCs) or human embryonic stem cells has been shown to efficiently trigger conversion to neurons. Here we describe two gene-edited hiPSC lines harbouring a doxycycline (DOX)-inducible cassette in the AAVS1 locus driving expression of NGN2 (BIONi010-C-13) or NGN2-T2A-GFP (BIONi010-C-15). By introducing NGN2-expressing cassette, we reduce variability associated with conventional over-expression methods such as viral transduction, making these lines amenable for scale-up production and screening processes. DOX-treated hiPSCs convert to neural phenotype within one week and display the expression of structural neuronal markers such as Beta-III tubulin and tau. We performed functional characterization of NGN2-neurons co-cultured with hiPSC-derived astrocytes in a “fully-humanized” set up. Passive properties of NGN2-neurons were indistinguishable from mouse primary cells while displaying variable activity in extracellular recordings performed in multi-electrode arrays (MEAs). We demonstrate that hiPSC-derived astrocytes and neurons can be co-cultured and display functional properties comparable to the gold standard used in electrophysiology. Both lines are globally available via EBISC repository at <https://cells.ebisc.org/>.

1. Introduction

The differentiation potential of human-induced pluripotent stem cells (hiPSCs) represents a paradigm shift in neuroscience research as it enables access to an unlimited amount of human brain cells. Neuronal differentiation protocols such as dual-SMAD inhibition have been used since the discovery of hiPSC technology (Chambers et al., 2009). However, yield and cell type is highly variable and the number and proportion of excitatory versus inhibitory neurons changes over batches and across genetic backgrounds (Micali, 2020).

The concept of cell reprogramming has also been applied to force the differentiation of somatic cells to neurons (Zhang et al., 2013) and is called *trans*-differentiation. Forced differentiation mediated by Neurogenin2 (NGN2) overexpression enables the generation of a more homogeneous cell population, minimizing batch-to-batch variability issues while accelerating the first stages of differentiation. However, NGN2

overexpression does not reduce the maturation time required to have functional neurons *in vitro*, which normally goes beyond 60 days and requires the presence of matricellular support provided by a third cell type, preferably astrocytes (Hillen et al., 2018).

CRISPR/Cas9 technology enables site-specific introduction of overexpression cassettes into safe loci of the genome, achieving 100% expression in each cell in culture and overcoming heterogeneity due to viral transduction. Here, we combined the model described by Zhang and collaborators in 2013 with gene editing to generate two cell lines carrying a doxycycline-inducible cassette to regulate NGN2 expression. We co-cultured NGN2-neurons with hiPSC-derived astrocytes to validate a *humanized assay* that displays passive properties comparable to mouse primary cultures. hiPSC lines and methods described are available via www.EBISC.org.

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: acabrer8@its.jnj.com (A. Cabrera-Socorro).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scr.2021.102386>

Received 2 December 2020; Received in revised form 15 March 2021; Accepted 30 April 2021

Available online 24 May 2021

1873-5061/© 2021 Janssen Pharmaceutica NV. Published by Elsevier B.V. This is an open access article under the CC BY license

(<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

2. Material AND methods

2.1. Maintenance and expansion of hiPSCs:

Bioni10C-13 and Bioni10C-15 hiPSC lines were cultured in Matrigel coated 6-well plates in mTeSR1 medium with complete medium change on daily basis. Cells were split when they reached a density of 80% either with EDTA or accutase. All standard protocols used have been already published and are available at EBiSC.org.

2.2. Neuronal differentiation

For neuronal differentiation by NGN2 overexpression, hiPSCs were split with accutase and plated in Matrigel coated 6-well plates at a density of 10×10^4 cells/cm² with 10uM Rock inhibitor (Sigma, Y-0503) on day-0 (see scheme in Fig. 1B). From day 1–3, half of medium was changed with fresh N2B27 supplemented with doxycycline (2 µg/ml). On day 4, cells were split with accutase for co-culture with hiPSC-derived astrocytes or frozen down in mFreSR for future use. Doxycycline supplement was kept in culture media during the first 15 days of differentiation and then removed. Neuron-astrocyte co-cultures were maintained for up to 60 days in “N2B27” medium composed of: 50% mixture of DMEM/F12 (31331-028) and Neurobasal medium (21103-049) supplemented with N-2 supplement (17502-048), B-27 supplement (17504-044), Glutamax (35050-038), non-essential amino acids (11140-035), 0.5 mM of sodium pyruvate (11360-070), β-mercaptoethanol (31350-010), Penicillin/Streptomycin (15140-122, all from Gibco/Thermo Fisher Scientific) and 2.4–2.9 µg/mL human insulin (Sigma I9278).

2.3. Generation of iPSC-derived astrocytes

Astrocytes with dorsal regionalization identity were differentiated from cortical neuronal progenitor cells (NPCs) as previously described (Emdad et al., 2012; Hedegaard et al., 2020). 25–30 days differentiated NPCs were generated from the iPSC line IPSC0028 (Sigma Aldrich) following already published protocols (Shi et al., 2012; García-León et al., 2018) and kept as frozen stocks. NPCs were thawed and cultured in glial induction media (GIM) composed of N2B27 and 20 ng/mL of human recombinant CNTF (R&D Systems, 257-NT) for 2 weeks. Subsequently, GIM was replaced by astrocyte culture media (ACM) composed of MEM (Life Technologies; 11095–080) supplemented with 10% Horse Serum (Life Technologies; 26050–088, heat inactivated) and 0.6% glucose. Astrocytes could be maintained in culture for months or frozen down, and were only used for co-cultures after 120 days of differentiation.

2.4. Rat primary cortical neurons and astrocytes

Rat primary cultures were used as a standard reference in MEA activity pattern. All reported studies described here have been conducted following “The provision of the European Convention” on the protection of vertebrate animals which are used for experimental and other scientific purposes, and with “the Appendices A and B”, made in Strasbourg on March 18, 1986 (Belgian Act of October 18, 1991). All experimental protocols were approved by the ethical committee of Janssen Pharmaceutica N.V. Primary neurons were freshly dissociated from embryonic E18-19 rat cortices and plated onto 48-well MEA plates (Maestro system, Axion Biosystems) as described previously (Kreir, 2018). Rat primary astrocytes were prepared as previously reported (Garcia-Leon, 2018 #178).

2.5. Immunofluorescence

Neurons and astrocytes were co-cultured in a 50/50% mixture in 96-well plates pre-coated with PLO/Laminin at a density of 25,000 cells/

well. Cells were fixed at different time points by adding 4% paraformaldehyde diluted in phosphate buffer saline (PBS) during 10–15 min. After fixation, cells were permeabilized for 15 min with 0.25% solution of Triton-X100 in PBS (permeabilization buffer), and subsequently blocked with 1% bovine serum albumin (BSA) diluted in permeabilization buffer. All antibodies (primary and secondary) were diluted at 1:700 in permeabilization buffer supplemented with 1% goat serum. Incubation with the following primary antibodies was done for 1–2 h: HT7, (ThermoFisher, Ref# MN1000), GFAP (Millipore, Ref# IF03L), Beta-III tubulin (Abcam, Ref# ab18207) and MAP2 (Aves Lab, Ref# MAP0607). Secondary antibodies were incubated for 1 h before staining with Hoechst for nuclear detection. Imaging was performed with the Opera Phenix® high content imaging system.

2.6. Measurement of soma size

The total surface area of iPSC cell soma was determined using Fiji open source software.

2.7. Gene expression analysis

RNA was harvested using the RNeasy Micro Kit (Qiagen) following the manufacturer’s Gene expression analysis was performed via reverse transcription real time qPCR (RT-qPCR). First, RNA was harvested using the RNeasy Micro Kit (Qiagen) following the manufacturer’s instructions. Briefly, the cells were lysed with the provided RLT buffer. Using the provided columns, the mRNA was collected, washed, treated with DNase and then eluted in RNase-free water. RNA concentration was determined via the Nanodrop microvolume spectrophotometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific) and 500 ng RNA per sample was reverse transcribed. Reverse transcription was performed with the High Capacity Reverse Transcription Kit (Thermo Fisher Scientific) for 2 h at 37 °C. Real time PCR was conducted on the Quantstudio 7 using the 2^{-ΔΔCt} method in combination with hydrolysis probes (TaqMan™, Applied Biosystems). First, CTs were normalised against the geometric mean of three endogenous control genes (GAPDH, HPRT1 and GUSB) as well as the calibrator sample (hiPSC at day 0). For each sample, three technical replicates and for each condition three biological replicates were averaged. Analysis of the acquired RT-qPCR data was performed with the Quantstudio software (Applied Biosystems). The TaqMan assay IDs are given in Table 1.

2.8. Electrophysiology

For whole-cell patch-clamp recordings, individual coverslips were transferred into a recording chamber and continuously perfused (1.5 ml min⁻¹) with artificial cerebrospinal fluid (ACSF) bubbled with a mixture of CO₂ (5%) and O₂ (95%) at room temperature. ACSF contained (in mM) 124NaCl, 2.7 KCl, 1.25 NaH₂PO₄·H₂O, 26 NaHCO₃, 18 glucose, 2 ascorbic acid, 2 CaCl₂, 1.3 MgSO₄ (pH 7.3, 300–310 mOsm). Recordings were made using borosilicate glass pipettes with a resistance of 3–5 MΩ, pulled on a horizontal puller (P-97, Sutter Instrument Co.). Signals were amplified (Multiclamp 700B, Molecular Devices) and digitized (Digidata 1440A, Molecular Devices) and recorded in pCLAMP 10 (Molecular Devices). Series resistance was monitored before, during, and after recording. Cells were discarded if the series resistance deviated more than 20% from its value at the start of recording, or if it exceeded 30 MΩ. For current-clamp records, patch pipettes were back-filled with (in mM) 135 K-gluconate, 5 KCl, 2 NaCl, 10 HEPES, 0.2 EGTA, 10 phosphocreatine, 4 Mg-ATP and 0.4Na-GTP (pH7.3, ±290 mOsm). The passive membrane properties and the characteristics of the action potential were obtained by injecting a series of 500ms long current steps with increasing amplitudes. Resting membrane potential (RMP) was measured as the voltage with no injected current. Liquid junction potential was not corrected for. The input resistance (R_{input}) was estimated as the linear slope of the current–voltage (I-V) relationship of the last 50 ms by a –50

Fig. 1. Gene editing strategy and characterization of NGN2 neurons and iPSC-derived astrocytes. (A) gene editing strategy followed to introduce the NGN2 (or NGN2-eGFP for BIONi010-C-15 line) inducible cassettes (more details in [Schmid et al., 2021](#)). (B) workflow scheme describing steps and timelines for differentiation of NGN2-inducible lines into neurons. Representative images of first four days of differentiation are shown. (C) Expression levels of key stem cell and neuronal markers quantified by q-RT-PCR over the first 14 days of differentiation. (D-F) Representative images of iPSC-derived astrocytes shown in bright field images (D) and stained for astroglial marker GFAP at 8 and 30 days *in vitro* (DIV, E and F). GFs, growth factors.

Table 1

TaqMan probes.

Gene	TaqMan Assay ID	Gene	TaqMan Assay ID
<i>GAPDH</i>	Hs99999905_m1	<i>NEUROD1</i>	Hs01922995_s1
<i>GFAP</i>	Hs00909233_m1	<i>PAX6</i>	Hs00240871_m1
<i>GUSB</i>	Hs99999908_m1	<i>POU5F1</i>	Hs04260367_g1
<i>HPRT1</i>	Hs99999909_m1	<i>SLC17A7</i>	Hs00220404_m1
<i>MAP2</i>	Hs00258900_m1	<i>Sox2</i>	Hs01053049_s1
<i>NES</i>	Hs04187831_g1	<i>TUBB3</i>	Hs00801390_s1

pA hyperpolarizing step. Relations between firing frequency and injected current were examined by measuring action potentials elicited by each step starting from RMP. Properties of action potentials were determined for the first action potential elicited by injection of +200 pA step.

For Multi-Electrode Array (MEA) recordings, human NGN2-neurons were co-cultured with hiPSC-derived astrocytes in 1:1 ratio and plated onto 48-well MEA plates (Axion BioSystems) coated with polyethyleneimine and laminin as described earlier (García-León et al., 2018). Spontaneous network activity of the neurons was recorded for 5 min on specific time points using the Axion Biosystems Maestro MEA at 37 °C and 5% CO₂. Data analysis was performed using AxIs software (Axion Biosystems Inc.) and Prism 8 (GraphPad Software). Active electrodes, (AEs; 16 electrodes per well) were defined as electrodes averaging more than 5 spikes per minute. Active wells were defined as those that have more than 30% of active electrodes. All wells that did not comply with these criteria were discarded. The threshold for spike detection was defined as ≥ 5.5 -fold the standard deviation of the RMS (root mean square) noise. To be able to calculate the synchronicity of the neuronal culture, at least 25% of the total electrode in a well should participate to the network bursts.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Generation and differentiation workflow of two lines harbouring NGN2-inducible cassettes

Two cell lines were gene edited to carry a doxycycline (DOX-) inducible cassette into the safe harbor AAVS1 locus as described in Schmid et al. (2021). One AAVS1 locus was modified to carry a cassette that constitutively express rtTA protein (M2rtTA) under the CAG promoter, while the second AAVS1 allele was used to introduce the NGN2 sequence downstream the tetracycline response element (TRE, Fig. 1A). While the line BIONI010-C13 only expresses NGN2 upon DOX addition, the line BIONI010-C15 contains an additional EGFP sequence separated by a 2TA bi-cistronic sequence that enables cell traceability by fluorescent microscopy. Both lines can efficiently differentiate into neuronal progenitor cells (NPCs) by addition of 2 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ of DOX as described in the scheme of Fig. 1B and confirmed by RNA expression of key neural markers (Fig. 1C). Pre-differentiated NPCs can be frozen down after 4 days of DOX treatment. From one frozen vial of iPSCs, it is possible to generate up to 24–30 vials of 4-days induced NPCs (5×10^6 cells/vial) in 10–12 days.

3.2. Characterization iNGN2 neurons and hiPSC-derived astrocytes

To confirm the differentiation potential of Bioni10-C-13 and Bioni10-C15 into neuronal progenitors and neurons, we performed a time-course experiment, where RNA levels of classical neural markers were analysed. During the first 14 days of differentiation, we observed a marked reduction of stem cell markers such as Oct4 inversely proportional to the expression of early neural differentiation genes such as Nestin, Pax6 and MAP2, among others (Fig. 1C). We confirmed the expression of neuronal markers at protein level up to 30 days in culture by immunofluorescence with specific antibodies against MAP2, Tau and

Beta-III tubulin (Fig. 2B', 2D' and H').

3.3. Fully humanized assay

It is widely accepted that hiPSC-derived neurons do not display active and passive membrane properties amenable for electrophysiological studies unless co-cultured with astrocytes (Zhang et al., 2013; Bardy et al., 2015; Meijer et al., 2019). We have previously shown that hiPSC-derived neurons display activity as measured by extracellular recordings in multi-electrode arrays (MEAs) when co-cultured with murine astrocytes (García-León et al., 2018). As our goal is to establish a fully humanized assay, we opted for the generation of hiPSC-derived astrocytes using pre-differentiated frozen stocks of cortical NPCs as starting material. The generation of functional astrocytes from hiPSCs has been previously reported (Emdad et al., 2012; Hedegaard et al., 2020; Delépine et al., 2016). Therefore, we used the same protocol to generate the astrocytes to be co-cultured with the NGN2-induced neurons. As shown in Fig. 1D-F, these cells display the typical morphology of astroglia when maintained *in vitro*, and express the gold standard marker of astrocytes GFAP (Fig. 1E and 1F).

Once we validated and froze down stocks of astrocytes and neurons, we next proceeded to establish the co-culture conditions. The human prefrontal cortex has been described to have an astrocyte-to-neuron ratio of 1.75 (Sherwood et al., 2006), which can be considered as the most biologically meaningful standard to reproduce brain functional properties. Often, *in vitro* culture conditions provide excess and frequent replacement of nutrients that keep cells under low metabolic stress. Based on this we designed a co-culture assay in which the astrocyte-to-neuron ratio was reduced to 1, and therefore prepared 50/50% cell mixtures of NGN2-induced progenitors with hiPSC-derived astrocytes that were plated in different formats as explained in the method section. The scheme shown in Fig. 2A displays the different possibilities that the system offers, from the maintenance of NGN2 neurons as monocultures to the co-culture with astrocytes (or any other cell type) and the preparation of frozen stocks. Importantly, we have observed that only weekly media changing is enough to keep viable cultures, substantially reducing the costs associated with culture media composition. These cells were maintained for up to 2 months for functional characterization using multiple-electrode arrays and patch-clamp.

3.4. Co-culture characterization

We performed immunostaining to evaluate morphological properties and confirm the expression of key markers typically present in both cell types separately. NGN2 neurons and astrocyte co-cultures were fixed after 8, 16 and 30 days of differentiation. From the first time point, we observed glial (Fig. 2B-H) and neuronal markers (Fig. 2 B'-H') being expressed along the whole differentiation period. Importantly, the presence of astrocytes enables a homogeneous distribution in the cell culture surface that is normally lost in monocultures where clusters of cells are often observed. From 8DIV onwards, the expression of the glial marker GFAP is preserved and enables the traceability of the complex network that provides structural support to the neurons (Fig. 2F''-H''). On the other side, neurons show an increase in the expression levels of MAP2 over time that is accompanied by the expression of Tau. By day 30, we observed the formation of a complex neuronal network detected by the presence of Beta-III tubulin (Fig. 2H''). The expression of endogenous EGFP in Bioni10-C15 line can be detected during the whole differentiation timeline, although is more intense at the early stages when DOX is still added to the culture media (Fig. 2C' and 2E'). Our imaging data demonstrate that both cell types are viable when co-cultured, and confirms that the 1:1 ratio (astrocyte:neuron) allows long term cultures that display fundamental properties of both cell types as observed in brain tissue. Previous investigation of the geometry of pyramidal neurons has showed that human cell bodies are in general larger than the rodent ones (Benavides-Piccione et al., 2020). Our results

Fig. 2. Description of fully human co-culture of NGN2-neurons with hiPSC-derived astrocytes. (A) Shows the workflow and timelines used to prepare NGN2 monocultures (A-A), for co-culturing with astrocytes (A-B) or for preparing frozen stocks (A-C). (B-H'') BIONi010-C15 and BIONi010-C13 derived neurons showing expression of key neuronal markers when co-cultured with iPSC-derived astrocytes for 8 (B-C''), 16 (D-E'') and 30 days (F-H''). (I-I'') Representative images of monoculture of rodent primary culture (I) in comparison to Bion10-C13 line grown in culture for 30(I') and 60 days (I'') in the presence of human astrocyte. (J) Histogram of soma size comparison between different iPSC lines to rodent primary culture.

showed that the Bioni10-C13 neurons, when cocultured with human astrocyte for 60 days, developed a much larger soma size compared to the mature rodent neuronal cultures. The mean (\pm S.E.) soma area calculated from NGN2 neuronal images increased from $273.35 \pm 15.24 \mu\text{m}^2$ at 30 DIV to $724.97 \pm 45.36 \mu\text{m}^2$ at 60 DIV (Fig. 2I-J); while the soma size calculated from rodent primary cortical neurons is $269.92 \pm 10.12 \mu\text{m}^2$ at its maturity. This soma size can only be reached at 300 DIV when iPSC-derived neurons are cocultured with rodent astrocytes (Odawara et al., 2016).

Once the co-culture conditions were defined and confirmed by imaging, we set out to determine and characterize the functional maturation of co-cultured NGN2 neurons with electrophysiological recordings. As neurons develop, their physiological maturity is represented by two properties. The first one is their passive membrane properties, determined by the cells' morphology and the various level of expressed ion channels. Changes in these properties translate into proper recovery and activation of voltage gated cation channels needed for the proper generation of action potentials (APs). The second property consists of synaptic interactions with surrounding neurons. To evaluate these two properties, we firstly performed patch-clamp recordings, focusing on the temporal evaluation of passive membrane properties and synaptic currents. Considering rodent primary neuronal cultures (at 21 DIV) as a reference, we set out to assess and compare the passive membrane properties of the induced NGN2-neurons co-cultured with hiPSC-derived astrocytes (human assay). We also added two extra conditions: iPSC neurons generated with dual-SMAD inhibition co-cultured with mouse primary astrocytes (dual SMAD NPCs + astrocytes-m) and hiPSC neurons generated with dual-SMAD neurons co-cultured with human iPSC-derived astrocytes (dual SMAD NPCs + astrocytes-h). Fig. 3A shows the

passive membrane properties (resting membrane potential (RMP) and input resistance) as well as the action potential amplitude of these cultures at different timepoints. In general, a developing neuron can only be considered as mature if displaying a resting membrane potential (RMP) around -60 mV , mainly determined by the background potassium channel expression level. In fact, these are the values registered by *in vivo* patch-clamp in fully developed mouse, rats, and in human brain tissue (Ledri et al., 2015). It's important to notice that the RMP of neurons differentiated using classic dual-SMAD inhibition protocols never went below -60 mV , even after 75 days of differentiation. No differences were observed when using murine primary or iPSC-derived astrocytes (with murine astrocyte: $-42.41 \pm 2.42 \text{ mV}$, $n = 12$; with human astrocyte: $-43.48 \pm 1.45 \text{ mV}$, $n = 13$). Similarly, no differences were found when NGN2-neurons were co-cultured with either astrocytes after 30 days ($-45.02 \pm 3.33 \text{ mV}$, $n = 9$). Interestingly, the RMP of NGN2 neurons improved considerably along their development, and reached $-60.16 \pm 1.41 \text{ mV}$ at 60 DIV, a value comparable to the value observed in rodent primary cultures ($-59.42 \pm 1.99 \text{ mV}$, $n = 10$). Measurements of input resistance indicated a similar improvement at 45 DIV ($428.43 \pm 53.51 \text{ M}\Omega$, $n = 24$) and 60 DIV ($151.81 \pm 23.56 \text{ M}\Omega$, $n = 13$), reaching values that are consistent with the one obtained from human brain slices (Ledri et al., 2015) (Fig. 3B). Simultaneously, action potential amplitudes surpassed 100 mV after 45 days and remains stable throughout (Fig. 3C). Altogether, these data demonstrate that NGN2 neurons, when co-cultured *in vitro* with human astrocyte, gradually acquire all characteristic passive membrane features of primary neurons.

In addition to patch-clamp, multi-electrode array was used to characterize the human co-culture system. The Bioni10-C15 neurons were recorded at different time points to observe the spontaneous activity and

Fig. 3. Maturation of NGN2-inducible Neurons: Passive Membrane Properties. (A-C): Dot plots depict resting membrane potential (A), action potential amplitude (B), and input resistance (C) for iPSC neurons at each differentiation and astrocyte co-culture condition. $n = 9$ [dual SMAD NPC + murine astrocyte at D60], $n = 12$ [dual SMAD NPC + murine astrocyte at D75], $n = 13$ [dual SMAD NPC + human astrocyte at D75], $n = 9$ [NGN2 iPSC + murine astrocyte at D30], $n = 12$ [NGN2 iPSC + human astrocyte at D30], $n = 24$ [NGN2 iPSC + human astrocyte at D45], $n = 13$ [NGN2 iPSC + human astrocyte at D60], $n = 10$ [mature primary neuron]. Pooled data represent mean \pm SEM. (D) Example voltage traces of a cell from dual SMAD NPCs cocultured with murine (rat) astrocyte (light blue trace) and a cell from NGN2 iPSC cocultured with human astrocyte (red trace), in response to hyperpolarizing and depolarizing current steps (-50 and $+200 \text{ pA}$). The start of a representative spike train is inset in each plot to highlight differences in action potential waveform. (E) Evolution of the spontaneous firing represented by the number of spikes of the NGN2 iPSC neurons co-cultured with human astrocytes on the MEA over 42 DIV ($n = 2$ technical replicates). Comparison of the mean firing rate and network synchronicity (synchrony index) between the rat primary neurons and the NGN2 iPSC neurons co-cultured with human astrocytes (E') Spikes amplitude of the NGN2 iPSC co-cultured with human astrocytes on the MEA over 36 days in culture and compared to the rat primary neurons spikes amplitude at 28 DIV.

network behaviour of the co-culture. The emergence of spontaneous firing occurred before 16 DIV and kept increasing until 36 DIV. This increase of spontaneous firing until 36 DIV was also accompanied by an increase in amplitudes of detected spikes, suggesting an improvement in the maturity of neuronal firing. At 42 DIV, we observed a drop in the number of spikes. Interestingly, the mean firing rate and synchrony index of the human co-culture at 36 DIV are quite comparable to rodent primary neurons at 28 days in culture ($2.797 \text{ Hz} \pm 0.1537$ versus $3.287 \text{ Hz} \pm 0.1142$, and $0.7537 \text{ Hz} \pm 0.01031$ versus $0.7583 \text{ Hz} \pm 0.0151$, respectively) (Fig. 3E).

Next, we evaluated the synaptic maturation status of the human co-culture system starting from 30 DIV and followed until 60 DIV. Using voltage-clamp recordings (@ -70 mV) we determined the presence of spontaneous post-synaptic events (sPSC) in the human co-culture conditions and compared to human NGN2 neurons co-cultured with mouse astrocytes (Fig. 4A & 4B). We detected very few spontaneous post-synaptic currents in a handful of recorded cells of the human co-culture systems suggesting the absence of fully functional synapses. The absence of synaptic maturity was confirmed by the lack of synaptic responses even after local electrical stimulation (Fig. 4C) or by local puffing of glutamate (Fig. 4D). On the other hand, the presence of mouse astrocytes appeared to facilitate synaptic maturation as the NGN2 neurons displayed a robust pattern of spontaneous post-synaptic events at DIV 30 (Fig. 4A & 4B). Similarly, MEA recordings of firing frequency showed a lack of effect of high concentrations of glutamate, NMDA, or GABA, suggesting the absence of the respective synaptic receptors. Only acetylcholine was able to reduce the mean firing rate at higher concentrations (Fig. 4E).

4. Discussion

Many laboratories have independently shown that NGN2 overexpression facilitates the stem cell to neuronal transition at the morphological and molecular level (protein and gene expression). NGN2 insertion in AAVS1 locus has already been described, and we demonstrate here the efficiency of the same method in two different clones including extra features such as the presence of EGFP cassette that enables cell traceability (Meijer et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2017). It is often stated that NGN2-induced neurons “mature” faster, although the term is rather relative and lacks consensus. We have recently proposed that neuronal maturity could be defined by the functional properties of the cells, with the resting membrane potential as a key parameter to be considered. Alike human neurons, we suggest that RMP of hiPSC-derived neurons should be -60 mV or below to be considered as mature (Allsopp et al., 2019). Although the expression of pan-neuronal genes such as MAPT and TUBB3, or glutamatergic markers like SCL17A7 starts from the first day of NGN2 induction (Zhang et al., 2013), four to five weeks of differentiation are still needed to achieve functional properties amenable for electrophysiological studies (Meijer et al., 2019). NGN2 overexpression is necessary but not sufficient to achieve “functional maturity”, as demonstrated by the fact that astrocytes have always been used when studying active and passive properties of induced neurons (Zhang et al., 2013; Meijer et al., 2019; Ho et al., 2016; Bardy, 2015). Therefore, it’s necessary to assume that no electrophysiological study can be performed on iPSC-derived neurons unless they are co-cultured with glial (or *glial-like*) cells.

While the first publications were using primary murine astrocytes as the main source of astroglia (Zhang et al., 2013), the key potential of hiPSCs relies on their capacity to fully display human biology. The

Fig. 4. Maturation of NGN2-inducible Neurons: Synaptic Activities & Pharmacological Profile. (A) Representative traces of spontaneous PSCs (sPSCs) recorded at -70 mV in neurons derived from Bioni10-C13 line cocultured with human or mouse astrocyte. (B) Dot plot depicts the frequency of sPSCs from recorded iPSC neurons at each developmental and astrocyte co-culture condition. Pooled data represent mean \pm SEM. Insert, representative image of Bioni10-C13 line cocultured with mouse astrocyte. White arrows indicate the luxuriant cellular processes that not observed when cocultured with human astrocyte. (C) Examples of evoked synaptic responses in Bioni10-C13 line. With each recorded neuron (Rec), trains of stimuli were delivered to at least 3 neighboring neurons (Stim1, 2 & 3) with two different stimulus amplitude, 50 and 100 μA . Among the 68 pairings across the developmental period tested, no or little response was observed. Holding potential at -70 mV . (D) Puff application of glutamate (2 mM) induced no significant current on recorded iPSC. The tip of the puff pipette (Puff) was carefully positioned close to the iPSC (Rec). Scale bar: 20pA and 200 ms. (E) Response on the mean firing rate of the NGN2 iPSC co-culture with human astrocytes to glutamate, NMDA, GABA and acetylcholine. Glutamate: concentration: Conc 1: 0.3 μM ; Conc 2: 1 μM ; Conc 3: 3 μM ; Conc 4: 10 μM ; NMDA: concentration: Conc 1: 0.3 μM ; Conc 2: 1 μM ; Conc 3: 3 μM ; Conc 4: 10 μM ; GABA: concentration: Conc 1: 0.1 μM ; Conc 2: 0.3 μM ; Conc 3: 1 μM ; Conc 4: 3 μM ; Acetylcholine: concentration: Conc 1: 1 μM ; Conc 2: 10 μM ; Conc 3: 100 μM ; Conc 4: 1000 μM .

comparison of murine and human primary astrocytes shows that human primary astrocytes do perform less efficiently when co-cultured with iPSC-derived neurons (Rhee et al., 2019). In addition, primary human astrocytes are difficult to access, display high batch-to-batch variability and are relatively expensive. The capacity of hiPSC-derived astrocytes to support activity in dual-SMAD neurons has been recently studied (Hedegaard et al., 2020). Although hiPSC-astrocytes support passive properties comparable to rat primary ones, the resting membrane potential of iPSC-derived neurons remained around -42 mV. By combining hiPSC-derived astrocytes and inducible NGN2 neurons we have achieved passive properties not described before, making the membrane properties of NGN2-neurons indistinguishable from murine primary cultures. In two different clones, Bioni10-C13 and Bioni10-C15, we demonstrate that a RMP of -60 mV is consistently achieved after 60 days of co-culturing. These NGN2 neurons also achieved a larger action potential amplitude and a smaller input resistance after 60 days of co-culturing. This could be due to a maturation of membrane channels leading to a decrease in membrane resistance. In our experience the most critical factor to achieve such optimal properties is the differentiation time of astrocytes that must be above 120 days.

Patch-clamping provides unique insights to functional properties of neurons, while it is a laborious technology with limited sampling size as compared to other techniques that also assess neuronal activity. Multi-Electrode Arrays (MEAs) provide an opportunity to increase the throughput of electrophysiological readouts by performing extracellular recordings. Despite having less resolution, MEAs enable the study of network activity in a highly controlled environment. Here we performed, for the first time, extracellular recordings of human NGN2 and hiPSC-derived astrocyte co-cultures in 48-well MEA plates. Remarkably, after 36 days of co-cultures we observed a synchrony index comparable to murine primary cultures (Fig. 3E).

As the scientific community keeps using the model, we learn more about the nature of NGN2 neurons. Even with the use of small molecules to force the dorsal-telencephalic fate and an excitatory profile, NGN2-induced neurons do not display a forebrain identity. In the most thorough descriptions of the model it has been unambiguously shown that NGN2-neurons lack of key cortical markers such as TBR1 (Nehme et al., 2018; Zhang et al., 2013). In fact, it has been suggested that Neurogenin2 overexpression triggers a fate towards spinal motor (expressing Vacht and Olig2) and sensory neurons (expressing Ret and Ntrk1) (Aydin et al., 2019). Here, we focused our efforts on the passive properties of NGN2 neurons co-cultured with iPSC-astrocytes as a preliminary step to consolidate optimal culture conditions, but future work will be needed to modulate the identity of these cells and further characterize their pharmacological properties.

5. Conclusion and summary

Here, we described the functional properties of neurons differentiated from two iPSC gene-edited lines to harbouring a NGN2-doxycycline inducible cassette into the AAVS1 locus. We demonstrated their capacity to display optimal passive membrane properties (eg as observed in human brain tissue) when co-cultured with hiPSC-derived astrocytes while they only showed signs of synaptic maturity when co-cultured with mouse astrocytes. Remarkably, these neurons presented intrinsic properties such as RMP and input resistance that were indistinguishable from murine primary neurons, the standard used in electrophysiology. We explain in detail the protocol for their differentiation and co-culture, which can be adapted for scaling up production and to supply to laboratories with limited stem cell experience. These lines are deposited in the European Bank of iPSCs (EBiSC.org) and can be accessed globally.

Funding

The EBiSC – European Bank for induced pluripotent Stem Cells project has received support from the Innovative Medicines Initiative

Joint Undertaking under grant agreement n° 821362, resources of which are composed of financial contribution from the European Union and EFPIA companies' in-kind contribution.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Pei-Yu Shih: Data curation, Investigation, Methodology, Writing - review & editing. **Mohamed Kreir:** . **Devesh Kumar:** Data curation, Investigation, Methodology, Writing - review & editing. **Frederik Seibt:** Data curation, Investigation, Methodology, Writing - review & editing. **Francisco Pestana:** Data curation, Investigation, Methodology, Writing - review & editing. **Benjamin Schmid:** Methodology, Investigation, Writing - review & editing. **Bjørn Holst:** Methodology, Investigation, Writing - review & editing. **Christian Clausen:** Methodology, Investigation, Writing - review & editing. **Rachel Steeg:** Data curation, Investigation, Methodology, Writing - review & editing. **Benjamin Fischer:** Data curation, Investigation, Methodology, Writing - review & editing. **Juan Pita-Almenar:** Data curation, Investigation, Methodology, Writing - review & editing. **Andreas Ebnet:** Data curation, Investigation, Methodology, Writing - review & editing. **Alfredo Cabrera-Socorro:** Conceptualization, Data curation, Investigation, Methodology, Writing - original draft.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgments

The EBiSC – European Bank for induced pluripotent Stem Cells project has received support from the Innovative Medicines Initiative Joint Undertaking under grant agreement n° 821362, resources of which are composed of financial contribution from the European Union and EFPIA companies' in-kind contribution.

References

- Allsopp, T.E., Ebnet, A., Cabrera-Socorro, A., 2019. Deploying human pluripotent stem cells to treat central nervous system disorders: facts, challenges and realising the potential. *Stem Cell Res.* 41, 101581.
- Aydin, B., et al., 2019. Proneural factors *Ascl1* and *Neurog2* contribute to neuronal subtype identities by establishing distinct chromatin landscapes. *Nat. Neurosci.* 22 (6), 897–908.
- Bardy, C., et al., 2015. Neuronal medium that supports basic synaptic functions and activity of human neurons in vitro. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA* 112 (20), E2725–E2734.
- Bardy, C., et al., 2015. Neuronal medium that supports basic synaptic functions and activity of human neurons in vitro. *PNAS* 112, E2725–34.
- Benavides-Piccione, Ruth, et al., 2020. Differential Structure of Hippocampal CA1 Pyramidal Neurons in the Human and Mouse. *Cerebral Cortex* 21 (30), 730–752. <https://doi.org/10.1093/cercor/bhz122>.
- Chambers, S.M., Fasano, C.A., Papapetrou, E.P., Tomishima, M., Sadelain, M., Studer, L., 2009. Highly efficient neural conversion of human ES and iPS cells by dual inhibition of SMAD signaling. *Nat. Biotechnol.* 27 (3), 275–280.
- Delépine, C., et al., 2016. Altered microtubule dynamics and vesicular transport in mouse and human MeCP2-deficient astrocytes. *Hum. Mol. Genet.* 25 (1), 146–157.
- Emdad, L., D'Souza, S.L., Kothari, H.P., Qadeer, Z.A., Germano, I.M., 2012. Efficient differentiation of human embryonic and induced pluripotent stem cells into functional astrocytes. *Stem Cells Dev.* 21 (3), 404–410.
- García-León, J.A., et al., 2018. Generation of a human induced pluripotent stem cell-based model for tauopathies combining three microtubule-associated protein TAU mutations which displays several phenotypes linked to neurodegeneration. *Alzheimers Dement* 14 (10), 1261–1280.
- Hedegaard, A., et al., 2020. Pro-maturational Effects of Human iPSC-Derived Cortical Astrocytes upon iPSC-Derived Cortical Neurons. *Stem Cell Rep.* 15 (1), 38–51.
- Hillen, A.E.J., Burbach, J.P.H., Hol, E.M., 2018. Cell adhesion and matricellular support by astrocytes of the tripartite synapse. *Prog. Neurobiol.* 165–167, 66–86.
- Ho, S.-M., et al., 2016. Rapid *Ngn2*-induction of excitatory neurons from hiPSC-derived neural progenitor cells. *Methods* 101, 113–124.
- Kreir, M., et al., 2018. Do in vitro assays in rat primary neurons predict drug-induced seizure liability in humans? *Toxicol. Appl. Pharmacol.* 346, 45–57.

- Ledri, M., et al., 2015. Differential Effect of Neuropeptides on Excitatory Synaptic Transmission in Human Epileptic Hippocampus. *J. Neurosci.* 35 (26), 9622–9631.
- Meijer, M., et al., 2019. A Single-Cell Model for Synaptic Transmission and Plasticity in Human iPSC-Derived Neurons. *Cell Rep* 27 (7), 2199–2211.e6.
- Micali, N., et al., 2020. Variation of Human Neural Stem Cells Generating Organizer States In Vitro before Committing to Cortical Excitatory or Inhibitory Neuronal Fates. *Cell Rep* 31 (5), 107599.
- Nehme, R., et al., 2018. Combining NGN2 Programming with Developmental Patterning Generates Human Excitatory Neurons with NMDAR-Mediated Synaptic Transmission. *Cell Rep* 23 (8), 2509–2523.
- Odawara, A., et al., 2016. Physiological maturation and drug responses of human induced pluripotent stem cell-derived cortical neuronal networks in long-term culture. *Scientific reports* 6, 26181. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep26181>.
- Rhee, H.J., et al., 2019. An Autaptic Culture System for Standardized Analyses of iPSC-Derived Human Neurons. *Cell Rep* 27 (7), 2212–2228.e7.
- Schmid, B., et al., 2021. Generation of two gene edited iPSC-lines carrying a DOX-inducible NGN2 expression cassette with and without GFP in the AAVS1 locus. *Stem Cell Res.* 52, 102240 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scr.2021.102240>.
- Sherwood, C.C., et al., 2006. Evolution of increased glia-neuron ratios in the human frontal cortex. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA* 103 (37), 13606–13611.
- Shi, Y., Kirwan, P., Livesey, F.J., 2012. Directed differentiation of human pluripotent stem cells to cerebral cortex neurons and neural networks. *Nat. Protoc.* 7 (10), 1836–1846.
- Wang, C., et al., 2017. Scalable Production of iPSC-Derived Human Neurons to Identify Tau-Lowering Compounds by High-Content Screening. *Stem Cell Rep.* 9 (4), 1221–1233.
- Zhang, Y., et al., 2013. Rapid single-step induction of functional neurons from human pluripotent stem cells. *Neuron* 78 (5), 785–798.